

Focus Group Semi-Structured Interview Script of Stakeholders’ Perspectives Regarding the Use of GAI in Science Education

1. INSTRUMENT DESCRIPTION

This Semi-structured focus group guide is grounded in two established theoretical frameworks: the Intelligent TPACK model and the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), which are instrumental in understanding the multifaceted dimensions of technology integration in educational settings. This data collection instrument aimed to capture: i) indicators of respondents' literacy in GAI in science education, ii) the GAI perceived ease of use in science education and GAI tools learning curve, iii) perceived usefulness of GAI tools in enhancing science education, iv) the perceived trust in GAI tools for science education content creation and factors influencing it, v) perceptions on knowledge needed for GAI integration in science education, vi) perceptions on the acceptance of GAI tools in science education, and vii) perceptions regarding GAI ethical issues in science education.

1.1. GAI Literacy

This dimension evaluates foundational competencies regarding GAI, focusing on conceptual understanding, tool recognition, productivity enhancement, and evaluative use, as depicted in Table 1. Questions probe how respondents define GAI, identify AI-powered tools, and apply GAI tools in science education settings. Items are derived from validated AI literacy constructs from both Chiu et al. (2024) and Al-Abdullatif (2024) and are supplemented with probing sub-questions that deepen inquiry into user knowledge and experience.

Table 1. Section of the instrument dedicated to the dimension of GAI Literacy

Dimension / Objective	Questions	Probing Questions
GAI Literacy / To collect indicators of respondents' literacy in GAI in science education	1. Can you explain what Generative Artificial Intelligence is?	1a. Please define the concept as you understand it. 1b. What examples would you use to illustrate what Generative Artificial Intelligence is?
	2. How can people determine if new tools are based, or not, in Generative Artificial Intelligence?	2a. Can you illustrate with an example? 2b. What characteristics indicate that a tool uses Generative Artificial Intelligence?
	3. How can people use GAI tools in science education for greater efficiency?	3a. Illustrate, by referring to concrete tasks and objectives (in science education) that can be accomplished/achieved more efficiently through the use of GAI tools.
	4. How can people choose GAI tools that are adequate for carrying out a given task in science education?	

1.2. GAI Perceived Ease of Use

This dimension is dedicated to discussing GAI perceived ease of use in science education and GAI tools learning curve, as prompted by the questions in Table 2. Adapting the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), this section investigates users' subjective ease of engaging with GAI tools. It includes queries about learning curves, clarity of use, and usability in teaching. The questions emphasize personal and vicarious experiences with learning GAI tools, exploring facilitators and barriers to skill acquisition.

Table 2. Section of the instrument dedicated to the dimension of GAI Perceived Ease of Use

Dimension / Objective	Questions	Probing Questions
Perceived Ease of Use of GAI tools / To assess the GAI perceived ease of use in science education and GAI tools learning curve	5. How easy or difficult is it to use IAG tools and what factors influence this?	5a. Can you illustrate with an example? 5b. What made it easy or difficult for you or for others you know?
	6. How easy or difficult is it to learn to use GAI tools?	6a. Can you describe your experience of building skills with GAI? 6b. What kinds of support, experiences, or strategies have helped you feel more competent using them?
	7. How easy or how difficult is it to use GAI tools for science education?	7a. Can you illustrate with an example?

1.3. Perceived Usefulness

This dimension seeks to assess the functional value educators assign to GAI tools in achieving instructional goals, as depicted in Table 3. Original items explore GAI utility in enhancing teaching performance, increasing productivity, and reducing effort. Sub-questions guide respondents to articulate concrete examples.

Table 3. Section of the instrument dedicated to the dimension of GAI Perceived Usefulness

Dimension / Objective	Questions	Probing Questions
Perceived Usefulness / To assess the perceived usefulness of GAI tools in enhancing science education	8. How useful can GAI tools be in science education?	8a. Can you illustrate with an example? 8b. Can you elaborate on its usefulness for achieving higher quality results/outputs or to reduce the time needed for a certain task? 8c. How does it affect the effort required to complete a task?

1.4. GAI Perceived Trust

Trust is a critical determinant of tool adoption. This dimension of the instrument aims to address the perceived trust in GAI tools for content creation in science education and factors that influence it, as shown in Table 4. Questions investigate whether users believe GAI tools provide reliable, secure, and expectation-aligned outputs. Additional probes explore concerns around data privacy, content veracity, and psychological comfort with AI-driven recommendations.

Table 4. Section of the instrument dedicated to the dimension of GAI Perceived Trust

Dimension / Objective	Questions	Probing Questions
GAI Perceived Trust / To assess the perceived trust in GAI tools for content creation in science education and factors influencing it	9. What factors affect people's trust and will to use GAI tools for content creation?	9a. Do you trust it? In what aspects do you (not) trust it? Can you illustrate with examples? 9b. Does knowing whether something is created with GAI affect your opinion or the way you use it? Why?
	10. How does users' sense of security and data privacy—or lack thereof—influence their willingness to use GAI tools?	10a. What kinds of security concerns come to mind about these tools? 10b. How do you weigh the potential benefits of GAI tools against the possible risks (e.g., privacy issues)?

1.5. Intelligent TPACK: Knowledge for GAI integration

This section assesses perceptions on knowledge that science teachers need to effectively integrate GAI tools in science teaching and learning, as shown in Table 5. This knowledge includes the ability to properly combine specific disciplinary content (Content Knowledge), pedagogical strategies (Pedagogical Knowledge) and GAI functioning (Technological Knowledge) tools, to pedagogically integrate GAI in lesson planning or adaptive instruction, for example. The questions in this section also probe the knowledge necessary for effective AI integration, such as understanding LLMs (large language models) for feedback or assessments.

Table 5. Section of the instrument dedicated to the dimension of Intelligent TPACK

Dimension / Objective	Questions	Probing Questions
Intelligent TPACK: Knowledge for GAI integration / To assess perceptions on knowledge needed for GAI integration in science education	11. What type of knowledge science teachers need to appropriately combine their teaching content, GAI tools, and teaching strategies to promote learning?	11a. Can you illustrate with an example? 11b. What teaching content is suited to be addressed in teaching strategies that include GAI? 11c. What GAI tools can be successfully used in science education? 11d. What teaching strategies can be explored in this context?
	12. What type of knowledge science teachers need to appropriately use GAI tools to foster assessment for learning and to assess processes?	12a. E.g., what GAI tools support monitoring students' learning, to provide real-time feedback and personalized learning to students, or to foster students' self-assessment? 12b. What challenges or limitations can happen when using GAI tools this way? E.g., could it be relevant to know how to use Large Language Models (LLM) to fill in a draft of students' assessment report?
	13. What type of knowledge science teachers need to use GAI tools to evaluate students' learning?	13a. What GAI tools can work well in this area (e.g., to generate quizzes)? 13b. What challenges or limitations can happen when using GAI tools this way?

1.6. GAI Acceptance

This dimension captures perceptions on the acceptance of GAI tools in science teaching and learning, namely affective and behavioral intentions toward GAI adoption, including enthusiasm, future use plans, and advocacy, as depicted in Table 6. It details how this dimension also directs to broaden the scope beyond educators to include other stakeholders (e.g., students, parents, administrators), and examines perceived value and barriers to institutional uptake.

Table 6. Section of the instrument dedicated to the dimension of GAI Acceptance

Dimension / Objective	Questions	Probing Questions
GAI Acceptance / To assess perceptions on the acceptance of GAI tools in science education	14. What are the perspectives among science teachers and students, parents and school heads about integrating GAI in teaching practice?	14a. E.g., how important is it to integrate GAI in science teaching and why? 14b. Can you illustrate with examples of situations when people revealed reservations or excitement about using these tools in science education? 14c. Should GAI adoption in science education be supported? How? Why?

1.7. GAI Ethics

This dimension focuses on perceptions regarding GAI ethical issues, as depicted in Table 7. Ethical considerations encompass responsible use, safety, well-being, and information security. Questions investigate the ethical literacy of educators and their capacity to teach these principles to students, emphasizing compliance, vigilance, and content protection.

Table 7. Section of the instrument dedicated to the dimension of GAI Ethics

Dimension / Objectiv Questions	Probing Questions
GAI Ethics / To assess perceptions regarding GAI ethical issues in science education	15. What topics do you consider important to include when discussing GAI ethics with students and colleagues?
	15a. What kind of guidelines or expectations should be set for responsible and safe GAI use, e.g., to ensure people's health and well-being while using it?
	16. What kinds of privacy and information security issues are important to consider when using AI tools in science education?
	16a. What steps should be taken to ensure that sensitive materials — like exams, grades, or student data — are protected when using GAI tools?